

CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY #1

—
**Leader: University Ca' Foscari
of Venice**

—
Milestones

M14

Seed stage of the first acceleration program

M15

Seed stage of the second acceleration program

M16

Validating the project results to support the
progression of the Ecosystem program

Table of Contents

Achievements.....	3
1. M14 – Seed stage of the first acceleration program	4
1.1 Executive summary.....	4
1.2 Activities carried out	5
1.3 Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented.....	9
1.4 Next steps and challenges	11
2. M15 – Seed stage of the second acceleration program.....	12
2.1. Executive summary.....	12
2.2. Activities carried out	13
2.3. Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented.....	14
2.4. Next steps and challenges.....	15
3. M16 – Validating the project results to support the progression of the Ecosystem program	16
3.1. Executive summary.....	16
3.2. Activities carried out.....	17
3.3. Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented.....	19
3.4. Next steps and challenges.....	20
Annexes	21

Achievements

CC #1 – List of main achievements and output achieved up to now (Milestones 14, 15 & 16)

M14	X	Self-explaining title of result achieved Max 2 lines for each item
	A	Planning and Validation: State of the art of Innovation Ecosystems - collection and study of international benchmarks and best practices - analysis of the existing activities supporting the entrepreneurial culture in the Spokes
	B	Pre-Acceleration: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting Specialists) - meetings with PL/PM and Committee, individual and collective presentations with SS - creation and maintenance of tools, templates and a shared repository
	C	Pre-Acceleration: Implementation of the 1st Scouting Stage - involvement of academic intermediaries, open calls - definition of the selection criteria, first selection funnel and Selection Day (19/03/2024)
	D	Pre-Acceleration: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training - collection of benchmarks on new start-ups creation roadmap and pitching, choice of freely available online training materials - drafting of a CC1 pitch deck template and recording of a video guide
	E	Pre-Acceleration: Open innovation activities - quali/quantitative analysis of a significant sample of companies to identify those with an innovative orientation in the North-East of Italy - identification and building of indicators of corporate innovation based on a review of scientific literature: R&D costs, patents, ROA
	F	Acceleration: Development of the Key Standardised Elements - reengineering of the HiT/uniTN Acceleration Framework (Peer learning driven. Goal: pitch ready for investors) - definition of a coaching and mentoring support system - multi-Spoke Physical Spaces Acceleration architecture
	G	Acceleration: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acc. officer, StartUp Analysts) - organisational boosting: selection and heading of coaches / mentors - invitation of external professionals and investors
	H	Acceleration: Implementation of the 1st Acceleration phase - 6 interactive workshops based on lean startup methodology, with a focus on peer learning and market validation - personalised ongoing coaching and pitch clinics to prepare startups for investor pitches at Demo Day
M15	I	Fundraising: Development of the Fundraising Network and Management - investors' networking - collaboration with banks: ABC in financing and contracts
	A	Pre-Acceleration: Implementation of the 2nd Scouting Stage (ongoing) - increased engagement of the CC1 Committee (CD) - process refining: targeted exploration and calls, BRL proactive support, Spokes' projects and patents screenings, improved involvement of academic intermediaries - external final evaluation for Selection Day #2
M16	A	Validation: data collection and elaboration for assessing the success rates - first analysis of the datasets of applications to the 1st Pre-Acceleration program - survey on accelerated teams satisfaction (midterm)

1. M14 – Seed stage of the first acceleration program

1.1 Executive summary

Max 1 page

This intermediate report follows the detailed, previous one consigned in February 2024, vertically developed with description of the individual Spokes' activities.

The structure of this report reflects the focus of the phases after the Pre-Acceleration, that, as the initial planning of the project, were asked to be conceived and articulated with a centralised perspective.

Specifically, in each Mx section we report the **Activities carried out**, the **Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented**, the **Next steps and challenges**.

In **M14** the focus of the description is tightly bound to the project context present at the beginning. Basically, the underlying variables are:

- the full comprehension of the project structure with a hands-on, operating view targeted on objectives, according to available roles and their competencies;
- the multi-disciplinary vs trans-disciplinary approach to be enabled, cultivated and implemented through the project roles;
- the presence of one-to-one more than one-to-many interactions in the system, to be headed towards an ecosystem in coherence with the Macro themes given to the Spokes and the RTs.

Indeed, a critical issue behind the project activities was the absence of a fully comparable, consistent benchmark as well as the responsibility to give birth to a very first experience in terms of academic-entrepreneurial ecosystem inspired by science and research.

You will find a list of the **activities** in M14: CC1.1 Planning and Validation, CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (1st round), CC1.3 Acceleration (1st round), CC1.4 Fundraising (1st round), with timing and thorough description of each Sub-Task, centred on the achievements perspective.

Then, the main **problems encountered** will be defined and supported with specific corrective actions, previously discussed and agreed among the different teams involved in carrying out the project.

Next steps and challenges is the last M14 topic: while the Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration phases could be reasonably considered as quite structured and ready for adjustments in M15 (2nd round), the Fundraising phase is about to define its own identity looking for a positive impact of the ideas/startups output, meeting the market expectations.

1.2 Activities carried out

Max 6 pages for each RT

The Pre-Acceleration phase of the 1st CC1 program - with a total of 179 applications - was completed in March 2024, leading to the selection of 15 startups that entered the Acceleration phase. During the Acceleration phase the 15 teams / startups took part in monthly in presence workshops (from April to September) and had the possibility to join a series of online webinars on specific topics. The teams were also offered support by both internal and external professionals, in the form of coaches and mentors. The Acceleration phase is about to be completed in October with the Demo Day #1 and the transition to the Fundraising phase.

Summary of iNEST's CC1 activities carried out for the 1st Acceleration Program

CC1.1 Planning and Validation (Leader: uniVE), **Timing:** December 2022 - August 2025

- Sub Task CC1.1.1: Planning of CC1 activities
- Sub Task CC1.1.2: Identification and analysis of successful practices of generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs among the iNEST Project Partners
- Sub Task CC1.1.3: Data elaboration

CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (Leader: uniVE), **Timing:** September 2023 - March 2024

- Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (Scouting Specialists "SS")
- Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the **1st Scouting Stage**
- Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training
- Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities

CC1.3 Acceleration (Leader: uniVR), **Timing:** March 2024 - October 2024

- Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardised Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) → uniTN + HiT
- Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) → uniTN + uniVE + uniVR
- Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the **1st Acceleration phase** → uniTN + uniVE

CC1.4 Fundraising (Leader: uniTS & PTAA), **Timing:** October 2024 - August 2025

- Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Fundraising Network and Management

Description of the carried out activities

As regards the **Sub-Task CC1.2.1**, the **engagement** and training activities consisted of:

- meetings with the Program Managers and Leaders and with the Spoke referents in the CD, to share the national and international benchmarks and define a harmonious strategy in the decentralised approach with respect to the engagement of the SS - for example: on the more or less binding role of the Spoke themes with respect to the Scouting graft, on the greater or lesser focus on spin-offs and patents, rather than on scouting and internal calls directed at researchers and students, depending on the settings chosen by the Spokes -, as well as to stimulate the issuing of calls for tenders relating to the SS not yet processed in some of the Spokes,
- individual and collective presentation meetings with the SS aimed at encouraging the sharing of previous professional experiences and the creation of a community among the SS based on peer learning, right from the start of the activity,
- creation and maintenance of shared repositories aimed at sharing documents and actions design,

- plenary meetings and individual meetings of SAL on CC1.2, continuously sharing the tools available - documents and project plans, minutes, reporting templates drawn up in concert with the Assistant Scouting Officers (ASOs) -, for the SSs.

As for the **Scouting Sub-Task CC1.2.2**, it took shape in the following activities:

- choice of the academic intermediaries to involve, in order to effectively reach the holders of innovative science-based ideas eligible for scouting (University Offices in charge of Research valorization, Department Directors, Professors responsible for research programs and funded projects, patents, spin-offs, Technology Transfer Offices / TTOs, entities involved in paths or competitions concerning start-ups, etc.), starting from and taking into account the initiatives already implemented by the individual Spokes outside of iNEST (see [Annex 1](#)),
- coordination of the open calls planning, supported by submission forms and of the contact actions aimed at knowledge, interviewing the actors who could indicate referents who bear entrepreneurial ideas, and the targeted collection of these,
- definition of the selection criteria by the CD (see [Annex 2](#)) and sharing with the SS,
- first selection / funnel (see [Annex 3](#)) and support for the development of the BRL, Business Readiness Level of the ideas (see [Annex 4](#)),
- application of the criteria by the SS,
- Selection Day and selection of the cohort participating in the Acceleration (15 teams / startups),
- definition of the contents of the legal documentation for the scouting participants in concert with uniPD – releases and GDPR –.

Furthermore

- for all engagement activities, a constant collaborative relationship was built with the team in charge of Communication: Spoke 9, SISSA.

As regards the **Online entrepreneurial training Sub-Task CC1.2.3**, it involved the following activities:

- Survey of existing literature with respect to the topics of investigation and ecosystem benchmarks,
- collection of good practices on the roadmap for the creation of new start-ups and pitching, choice of contents and online availability of training materials (see [Annex 5](#)),
- search for reference templates for pitches,
- drafting of the pitch script and recording of the clip illustrating the topics to be addressed for the aspiring start-up ideas (see [Annex 6](#)),
- harmonisation of the contents of the pitch with the evaluation criteria.

Regarding **Sub-Task CC1.2.4 on Open Innovation** and collaboration with companies, the main activities (still ongoing) are:

- to analyse a significant sample of companies to identify those with an innovative orientation in the North-East of Italy (Veneto, Trentino Alto-Adige, Friuli-Venezia Giulia),
- to identify and build indicators of corporate innovation based on a review of scientific literature: R&D costs, patents, ROA.

About the **Acceleration Framework development Sub-Task CC1.3.1**, it took shape in the following activities:

- re-engineering of the HiT/uniTN Acceleration Framework, stressing the importance of Peer learning and setting the goal of leading the startups to having their pitch ready for investors (Pitch Clinic approach),
- definition of a coaching and mentoring support system, with distinct functions
- definition of the workshop structure and physical spaces in a “travelling” architecture, changing location every month in order to maximise the role of the 9 Spokes,
- definition of an offer of online webinars on specific vertical themes.

As regards the **Engagement and coordination Sub-Task CC1.3.2**, it took shape in the following activities:

- creation of the Acceleration coordination and operative team, joining forces of uniVR, uniTN, HiT, uniVE and SISSA (for communication), setting weekly update meetings,
- organisational boosting: selection and heading of coaches / mentors;
- invitation of external professionals and investors.

On the other hand, the **Sub-Task CC1.3.3 (1st Acceleration phase)**, was articulated in the following activities:

- 6 interactive workshops based on lean startup methodology, with a focus on peer learning and market validation,
- 4 webinars on selected topics,
- personalised ongoing coaching and pitch clinics to prepare startups for investor pitches at Demo Day,
- first contacts with potential investors.

Date	Location	Sprint #	Workshop title
Friday 19 and Saturday 20 April	UNITS	1	Governance, Mission, Vision, Strategy and Business Model
			Problem and potential customer
Friday 10 and Saturday 11 May	UNIPD	2	Solution, value proposition and product POC
			Market, competitors and potential competitive positioning
Friday 31 May and Saturday 1 June	UniTN - Sol	3	Pitch session test
			Profit Model
Friday 5 and Saturday 6 July	SISSA	4	Operational model
			Economic-financial model
Friday 30 and Saturday 31 August	IUAV	5	Fundraising
			Company constitution and corporate governance
Friday 20 September	UNIVR	6	Pitch clinic
25 October	UNIPD	-	Demo Day

Date	Webinar
19 June	Presentation of psychological types
24 June	Marketing, customer acquisition, sales
5 July	IP strategy
September	Data protection
September	Legal issues - Shareholders' agreements, term sheets, investment agreements

Regarding the **Sub-Task CC1.4.1 on Development of the Fundraising Network and Management** (still ongoing), a work plan proposal was elaborated by Spoke 8 and approved by the CC1 Committee in August 2024. In particular PTAA, with the support of uniTS, will organise a series of activities taking into account the different maturity levels of the teams / startups accelerated in the 1st Acc. program. The offer includes:

- a short training on financing and contracts ABC
- meetings with banks of the North-East of Italy
- meetings with selected companies, with the "speed date" format

- external consulting for: startup evaluation and 1:1 support to the teams/startups in their path to fundraising and investor approaching
- a final event with national Business Angels networks.

Furthermore, with a spontaneous bottom-up approach, according to their portfolio focus, a first interest was collected by different investors such as: industrial, corporate and institutional funds and ventures, incubators, and even private equities.

1.3 Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented

Max 1 page for each RT

In the following, some plausible corrective actions are listed, related to the specific Sub-Tasks, by capitalising the 1st round hands-on experience.

→ = corrective action

As regards the **Sub-Task CC1.2.1 (Engagement and training of the Key actors)**, the main critical issues that arose and were addressed according to the enlarged team strategy are:

- delays in issuing calls for tenders relating to the SSs in some Spokes → ad hoc, bespoke solutions in collaboration with the administrative office of some of the Spoke leaders;
- difficulties in interpreting and implementing the official project documentation by the SSs, due to the specific Spokes internal procedures → creation and explanation of internal program presentations, with summary tables in the shared repository, and multiple interactions with each Spoke Administrative Department;
- difficulties in adopting the top-down correspondence between Spokes' themes and ideas to be collected → adaptive approach to the themes of the emerging ideas, according to the competences of the SSs and / or of the Spokes.

For the **Sub-Task CC1.2.2 (1st Scouting Stage)**, the main critical issues that emerged were:

- the challenge was the coming out for the CC1 path elements of differentiation, compared to the other existing ones, implemented by the Spokes (see [Annex 1](#)) → for round 2: refining of the distinctive elements of the CC1 offer (head-coaching, coaching, mentoring, acceleration platform) and of the selection criteria (subsets, weights, segmented focus);
- highlighting synergies and differentiation key factors with existing entrepreneurial contests, both local and national → for round 2: refining of the selection criteria accordingly;
- finding an alternative method to the third mission, that already favours the natural emergence of spin-offs, to intercept science-based ideas that are actually viable, especially centred from the point of view of the team capable of carrying them forward entrepreneurially → for round 2: development of guidelines for targeted scouting ("hunting").

As regards the **Sub-Task CC1.2.3 (Online entrepreneurial training)**, the main critical issues were:

- finding glocal benchmarks with similar ecosystem context characteristics → increased role of the knowledge base through online explanatory meetings centred on a SS professional community approach (convergence of Acceleration and Scouting phases checkpoints).

Considering the **Sub-Task CC1.2.4 (Open innovation)**, the main critical issues addressed were:

- consistency of the datasets extracted from the databases (quantitative approach);
- solidity of the chosen indicators:
 - R&D expenses, an indicator often underestimated in company balance sheets: companies are not required to detail R&D expenses in their balance sheets, which leads to incomplete disclosure of this information, as for strategic purposes they often avoid disclosing to competitors. In other cases there are obligations (e.g.: funded research), which further unbalance the survey, rewarding those who carry out research with public funding compared to self-financing
 - Patent royalties: it only captures the external valorization component of patent activity
 - Return on Asset (ROA): this indicator presents critical issues when it comes to evaluating R&D investments, which have long-term returns and are subject to great variability. This means that the use of ROA may not accurately reflect the value of innovation investments, penalising companies that invest heavily in R&D but do not yet see an immediate return on such investments. The economic fluctuations and the long timescales of R&D investments therefore make ROA an unreliable indicator for evaluating innovation.

→ The corrective action implemented on the quantitative side was the use of cross-reference approach to databases with related softwares; on the qualitative side, a complementary in-depth analysis with interviews involving key innovating companies by radical / disruptive R&D projects themes.

While for the **CC1.3.1 (Development of the Key Standardised Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces))**, the main critical issues addressed were:

- the 16 selected teams / startups were highly heterogeneous in background, maturity stage and acceleration needs → developing methodologies to handle a non-homogeneous cohort in terms of technology, maturity, and focus, including deep-tech and social impact startups, along with tailored validation methods;
- for some of the workshops the training load was too → integrating feedback to enhance the hands-on approach and create more opportunities for peer-learning despite the physical challenges of having a geographically distribute accelerator.

As regards the **CC1.3.2 (Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors)**, the main critical issues addressed were:

- difficulties in finding profiles with the optimal competencies mix for the role of Acceleration manager → intervention of a “task force” from uniTN and HiT, leveraging on previous experiences of Spoke 2 actors; constant support by the Scouting Officer and his team (uniVE);
- the commitment of some coaches was below expectations → improving the coach selection process with clearer commitment requirements.

As regards the **CC1.3.3 (Implementation of the 1st Acceleration phase)**, the main critical issues addressed were:

- the duration of the program (5-6 months) did not favour intense work and commitment by the selected startups, also considering the lack of a sharing and tracking tool → managing shorter acceleration cycles while maintaining lean startup quality and peer learning; identifying a platform/software to better manage the whole program (including startup engagement);
- the participation of some of the teams gradually dropped throughout the acceleration path, affecting their “readiness” for the Demo Day → ensuring strong individual coaching to prepare startups for investor pitches;
- difficulties in evaluating startup progression → defining metrics to better track startup progress and maturation in the program; implementing formal evaluation by the coaches; implementing a tracking platform.

Regarding the **CC1.4.1 (Development of the Fundraising Network and Management)**, the main critical issue could be:

- the feasibility and the positive approach to the banking tools suggested for financing perceived by the founders → potentiating the investor engagement strategy.

1.4 Next steps and challenges

Max 1 page for each RT

NEXT STEPS

CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (Leader: uniVE)

- Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities:
 - selection and engagement of the innovative companies in the North-East of Italy that are best matching with the CC1 objectives and topics, supported by qualitative analysis results;
 - definition of potential prizes by theme, innovation category;
 - Open Innovation Day #1 (TBD January / February 2025)

CC1.3 Acceleration (Leader: uniVR), **Timing:** March 2024 - October 2024

- Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the **1st Acceleration phase:**
 - Pitch Clinic of the 1st Acceleration Program (20/09/2024)
 - Demo Day #1 (25/10/2024) with invited potential investors
 - introduction to the Fundraising phase

CC1.4 Fundraising (Leader: uniTS & PTAA), **Timing:** October 2024 - August 2025

- Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation of the VC-Invested Stage:
 - final event particularly focused on Business Angels engagement
- Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage → uniPD
 - check and ahead roadmap for most promising startups emerging from the whole Acceleration program.

CHALLENGES

The upcoming challenge for the conclusion of the **1st Acceleration phase** is the successful implementation of the Demo Day of October 25th. The goals for this event are:

- boosting the Pitch Clinic pre-Demo Day activity to potentiate the startups presentations effectiveness;
- to involve more than 100 participants, of which a group of qualified investors;
- to engage the qualified investors as an external jury, using complementary evaluation criteria.

For what concerns the **Fundraising** task, the main challenge will be to lead to success at least 2 key startups of the cohort, by positively addressing the due diligence process and the following calibrated investments, enabling go to market strategies targeted on scalability.

2. M15 – Seed stage of the second acceleration program

2.1. Executive summary

Max 1 page

In **M15** the description capitalises on the lessons learned during M14 and the new underlying variables are:

- a more matured comprehension of the converging project roles and synergies, targeting on startup ideas and spin-offs within the team members;
- the shift from a one-to-one / one-to-many to a many-to-many interaction in the system, interpreting the coherence between the Macro themes and the roles of the Spokes, driven by the increasingly supportive CCI Committee supervision;
- an emerging awareness of the enabling tools that were analysed, shaped and refined with the project users perspective.

Particularly, the progressive implementation of a human-centred approach in performing the given Tasks / Sub-Tasks has demonstrated the crucial roles of the different project profiles proactively involved. Namely: TTOs and patent offices in the Pre-Acceleration phase, as much as the organisers of the Call for Ideas; coaches and mentors in streamlining and boosting the Acceleration phase, interpreting the Agile view; bottom-up sparkling initial interest of the different types of potential investors, with their different approaches (banking and finance) in the Fundraising phase.

You will find a list of the **activities** carried out in M15 so far: CC1.1 Planning and Validation, CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (2nd round), with timing and thorough description of each Sub-Task, centred on the achievements perspective.

Then, the main **problems encountered** will be defined and supported with specific corrective actions, previously discussed and agreed among the different teams involved in carrying out the project.

Details on the CC1.3 Acceleration (2nd round) and CC1.4 Fundraising (2nd round) Tasks are reported in the **Next steps and challenges** according to their actual implementation timing.

2.2. Activities carried out

Max 6 pages for each RT

The Pre-Acceleration phase of the 2nd CC1 program began in May-June 2024 with a deeper reflection on scouting approaches and a stronger commitment to targeted scouting (“hunting”), as suggested by the Program Leader. The continuous feedback from the SS and the Acceleration team, and the frequent debates of the CC1 Committee are now helping the refinement of the selection process and criteria.

Summary of iNEST's CC1 activities carried out for the 2nd Acceleration Program

CC1.1 Planning and Validation (Leader: uniVE), **Timing:** M04 – M040

- Sub Task CC1.1.1: Planning of CC1 activities
- Sub Task CC1.1.2: Identification and analysis of successful practices of generation and development of research start-ups and spin-off among the INEST Project Partners
- Sub Task CC1.1.3: Data elaboration
 - refinement of the tools for data collection (application forms)

CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (Leader: uniVE), **Timing:** June 2024 - December 2024

- Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting Specialists)
 - strengthening of the targeted scouting actions (“hunting”) by drafting two approaches to analyse patents and projects within the Spokes to identify potential entrepreneurs (see [Annex 7](#) and [Annex 8](#))
- Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the **2nd Scouting Stage** (Selection Day #2: TBC December 3rd, 2024)
- Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training
 - reinforcing the professional community management approach of SSs through continuous meetings, both plenary and individual.

The second round of the program is currently involving the iteration of the Pre-Acceleration phase, intervening in a manner consistent with the lessons learned in the 1st round, especially in search of an intensification of targeted contacts within the Spokes to bring out ideas and an increase in the density of relationships between the SS, placing recurring meetings of the Scouting team in the dates / locations of the Acceleration workshops (monthly frequency).

As of the beginning of September 2024 the Call for Ideas have already collected more than 100 applications.

2.3. Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented

Max 1 page for each RT

In the following, some plausible corrective actions are listed, related to the specific Sub-Tasks, by capitalising the 1st round hands-on experience.

→ = corrective action

As regards the **Sub-Task CC1.1.1 Planning of CCI activities**, the issues that arose were the opportunity to adjust and revise the general planned activities involving the CCI CD and the iNEST Scientific Committee, when necessary → choosing specific, mission critical emerging topics to be debated, stimulating the decision making process.

As regards the **Sub-Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors**, the issues that arose were:

- "innovation" viability → improvement in the analysis (e.g. Orbit) of the patents, while adopting a market-scalability approach (royalties)
- lack of action involving internal Spokes project leaders (PIs) shifting towards an iNEST whole ecosystem perspective → SS boost in engagement within Spokes, supported by CCI Committee.

As regards the **Sub-Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the 2nd Scouting Stage**, the issues addressed were:

- effective engagement strategies on targeted, internal intermediate actors within Spokes → ideathon, specific events with researchers, meetings with patent co-owners (external and internal).

2.4. Next steps and challenges

Max 1 page for each RT

NEXT STEPS

CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (Leader: uniVE), **Timing:** June 2024 - December 2024

- Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the **2nd Scouting Stage:**
 - refinement of the selection criteria;
 - pre-screening and screening of the applications by the SS;
 - CC1 Committee selection of the 30 teams that will take part in the 2nd Selection Day;
 - engagement of an external jury;
 - Selection Day #2 (TBC December 3rd, 2024).
- Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities

CC1.3 Acceleration (Leader: uniVR), **Timing:** January 2025 - July 2025

- Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardised Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces):
 - refinement of the Acceleration Framework based upon feedbacks and results;
 - Improvement of the content towards an even more hands-on approach and shorter acceleration cycles.
- Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts):
 - improvement of the coach selection process (higher commitment requirements) and coaching programme implementation;
 - refinement of metrics to measure startup maturation in the programme.
- Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the **2nd Acceleration phase:**
 - implementation of an acceleration platform (for managing the program, tracking progress, sharing file and updates);
 - new shorter acceleration cycle built on lean startup approach & peer learning;
 - an improved coaching programme.

CC1.4 Fundraising (Leader: uniTS & PTAA), **Timing:** February 2025 - August 2025

- Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Fundraising Network and Management
- Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation of the VC-Invited Stage
- Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage → uniPD

Specific actions for these Sub Tasks are to be defined according to the feedback collected from the 1st round.

CHALLENGES

Pre-Acceleration:

- overcoming the theme specific orientation in the pre-selection evaluation
- BRL effective improvement before the Selection Day
- use of a fully comprehensive platform to integrate Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration (SS and coaches).

Acceleration:

- initial assessment opportunity to differentiate the inbound level of the ideas
- lightening the workshop sprints' training components
- as-a-service mentors activities and webinar to deepen specific topics
- more focused coaching.

Fundraising:

- to organise the bottom-up investors interest by: idea stage of development, level of investment, and according to their portfolios.

3. M16 – Validating the project results to support the progression of the Ecosystem program

3.1. Executive summary

Max 1 page

In **M16** the description conveys the challenging effort of giving birth to a very first experience - with no similar precedents in the North East of Italy - and the underlying variables are:

- the absence of a fully comparable, consistent benchmark;
- the necessity for suitable and reliable metrics for the evaluation of: idea innovativeness, startup success factors, acceleration effectiveness, startup growth;
- an experimental approach, characterised by trial and error, in building evaluation and validation procedures.

As of September 2024 the only project phase for which data collection has already been completed is CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration (1st round), hence you will find a list of the **activities** carried out in M16 - CC1.1 Planning and Validation > Sub-Task CC1.1.3: data collection and elaboration - mainly with regard to the 1st scouting and Pre-Acceleration program.

After which the main **problems encountered** are listed and supported with specific corrective actions, previously discussed and agreed among the different teams involved in carrying out the project.

Useful insights on the CC1 outreach and significance for the ecosystem are emerging from descriptive statistics of the 1st data sample, with ongoing inferential testing attempting to find numerical evidence of supposed trends and relationships among variables.

Notwithstanding, the most critical and information-rich CC1 project phases in terms of Ecosystem progression are the Acceleration and Fundraising ones, having higher potential impacts on the involved territories, their research and productive systems, and their technology transfer strategies. The validation activities of these two phases are introduced in the last topic of M16, **Next steps and challenges**, and will take shape in the period leading to the beginning of the 2nd Acceleration round, allowing a more in-depth description in the next comprehensive report.

3.2. Activities carried out

Throughout the CC1 activities, the results data are gathered and elaborated for assessing the success rates of the Innovation Ecosystem with a deep focus on its Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration and Fundraising stages, in order to improve the innovation ecosystem's framework and support the progression of the same.

CC1.1 Planning and Validation (Leader: uniVE), Timing: December 2022 - August 2025

- Sub-Task CC1.1.3: data collection
 - repository of applications to the 1st program (179 applications)
 - survey on accelerated teams satisfaction (midterm)
- Sub-Task CC1.1.3: data elaboration
 - first analysis of the datasets of applications to the 1st program

So far the validation of the project results has focused on the **Pre-Acceleration** datasets, meaning on the 179 applications to the program, in order to reflect on:

- the attractiveness of the CC1 program
- the engaged target groups
- the efficacy of the Spokes diverse scouting approaches
- the selection process and the teams / startups traits facilitating the access to the Acceleration program.

The repository of applications was built by means of the "Call for ideas" or by direct filling by the Ss using the following fields:

Name and surname	Year of birth	Spoke	Applicant type	Name of your team/startup/idea	Describe your idea / project (Max 2000 characters)	Describe your team: competencies and relevant experiences of each member, eventual roles
------------------	---------------	-------	----------------	--------------------------------	--	--

The first step in the Pre-Acc. data elaboration was the classification of the applications, by matching the information contained in the answers to "**Describe your idea / project (max 2000 characters)**" with a set of explanatory categories, to be used both for descriptive analysis and for inferential statistics. Classification was accomplished by the two ASOs after experimenting with a number of coding tools that, after a thorough evaluation together with the PM, were not chosen because not suitable for the specificities of the database.

The chosen categories and levels were the following:

Type of solution (only 1 option)

- Process
- Product
- Service
- Product-service
- System
- Platform

Key technology (only 1 option)

- Hard
- Soft
- Hard and Soft
- Bio and nanotech
- No key technology

Innovation intensity (only 1 option)

- Radical
- Incremental
- The solution is not innovative

Macro theme / sector (only 1 option)

- Smart Industries & Digital
- Agrifood
- Health
- Living & Energy
- Cultural and Creative Industries
- Tourism
- Technologies and services for natural ecosystems

Key resources (1 or more options)

- Patent
- Non-patented technology
- Personal competencies
- Brand
- Material resources
- Financial resources
- No key resources

Team size (only 1 option)

- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-8
- 9-10
- >10
- no data

Team members qualifications (1 or more options)

- Bs
- Ms
- PhD
- Research Grant Holder
- Researcher
- Professor
- Non academic / Freelance
- no data

Team members key competencies

- Technical-scientific
- Economic and financial
- Management
- Marketing and communication
- Administrative
- Legal
- Humanistic and social
- Artistic
- no data

To reduce the incidence of subjective interpretation two independent classifications were carried out and compared, in order to obtain the complete dataset consisting of: 43 variables and 179 observations.

Descriptive statistics (some graphs are reported in [Annex 9](#)) allowed us to get an overview of the sample characteristics. For example, considering the **Type of solution** the mix of proposals was quite homogeneously distributed, with no strong prevalence of one type of solution over the others: 23% Product, 22% Service, 20% Platform, 15% System, 11% Product-service, 9% Process.

As regarding **gender**, there was a 60% of male applicants and 40% female applicants, with differences in the gender balance depending on the applicant type (for instance more balance in the Bs students group, less in the Professors group).

Nevertheless, it is worth noting that in the Selection stages (from Selection Form to accessing Acceleration) the female applicants were more successful than the male ones (F % from 32% in Selection Form to 44% in Acceleration).

Looking at the **Applicant type** per Spoke, it emerges that some Spokes were more effective in attracting Researchers and Professors, while other Spokes mainly engaged Students and/or Non academic professionals. This might be linked both to the different scouting approaches and to the specific SS background. Overall, the strikingly high proportion of Student applicants compared to more qualified academic applicants has highlighted, for the 2nd round, the need of “re-targeting” the scouting efforts and strengthening the targeted contacts (“hunting”).

Further analysing the content of the proposed ideas / projects, the majority of the solutions (43%) was based on “Soft” **Key technologies**, followed by “No key technology” (22%), “Bio and Nanotech” (15%), “Hard and Soft” (15%), and finally “Hard” (6%) technology.

The prevalence of Soft technologies is partly mirrored in the distribution of applications according to **Macro theme / sector**, which had “Smart Industries & Digital” at the top (28%), followed by Health (22%), Cultural and Creative Industries (17%), Living and Energy (16%), Tourism (7%), Agrifood (6%), and lastly Technologies and Services for Natural Ecosystems (4%).

Considering only the **16 startups selected** for the acceleration program, they do not appear to be particularly well distributed in relation to the Macro themes. In fact, over 56% (9 startups) are related to “Health Tech and Services”, while there appear to be no startups related to the themes of “Tourism” and “Cultural and Creative Industries”. The remaining selected startups display the following distribution: 19% are related to “Smart Industries and Digital”, 13% are related to “Smart and Sustainable Living”, 6% are related to “Smart Agrifood and Nutrition”, and 6% are related to “Technologies and Services for Natural Ecosystems”.

Inference testing is currently ongoing and the results will be available after the Demo Day and for the next reporting period.

3.3. Problems encountered and corrective actions implemented

In the following, some plausible corrective actions are listed, related to the specific Sub-Tasks, by capitalising the 1st round hands-on experience.

→ = corrective action

The main issue in data collection during the **1st Pre-Acceleration phase** was due to an initial usage of slightly different application forms by some of the Spokes, which was related to the difficulties in issuing calls for tenders for the SSs (causing misalignment of the Spokes in their scouting action, in terms of timing and tools). For this reason some applications had missing or incomplete data → a common tool and scouting repository was created and refined for the 2nd round

As for inferential statistics the main issue that arose was the small sample size (in some cases the “counts” are too low to guarantee adequate confidence in the interpretation of potential relationships) → all the tests will be repeated using as sample the applications to the 1st and to the 2nd Pre-Acceleration round.

3.4. Next steps and challenges

NEXT STEPS

1st round:

- **Pre-Acceleration phase data analysis:** completing inferential tests to assess relationships among variables
- **Acceleration phase data analysis:** multiple data sources will be used to evaluate the overall success and shortcomings of the 1st Acceleration Program. The main data sources for this stage are:
 - structured feedback from the participating teams / startups (15 teams / startups) (midterm and final survey)
 - quali-quantitative evaluation of the teams by their coaches (to be collected after the Pitch Clinic)
 - results of the 1st Demo Day (investors interest in the teams; external jury evaluations and prizes)
- **Fundraising phase data analysis**

2nd round: iteration and refinement of data collection and elaboration throughout the three phases (Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration, Fundraising).

CHALLENGES

The main challenges in validating the project results to support the progression of the Ecosystem program will be:

- the definition of metrics for the evaluation of the effectiveness of the Acceleration phase and of the Fundraising phase
- the collection of data on the progression of the teams / startups that did not access the Acceleration phase (those who did not “pass” the Selection Day) to allow a comparison with those who went through the acceleration path
- finding indicators to evaluate the impact of the whole CCI program with respect to the existing initiatives and programs offered by the individual Universities and institutions of the iNEST Consortium
- comparing the CCI results with other programs (at national and international level) that can be related to the CCI structure and offering.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Main initiatives already implemented by the Spokes outside of iNEST

CC1 Task	Initiatives	UNIBZ	UNITN	UNIUD	IUAV	UNIPD	UNIVE	UNIVR	SISSA	PAA	UNITS
Pre-Acceleration	Entrepreneurship courses		EIT								
	C-Lab										
	TTO/IP shared services									Area SciencePark	
	Active Scouting										
	Passive Scouting										
	Incubation - Active student scouting								Valorisation Off.		
	Entrepreneurial training				Starthub						
Hosting & facilities			Lab Village								
Acceleration	Mentoring		HIT - Trentino Startup Valley								
	Pitch building activities	NOI									
	Contest										
Funding	Investor Relation/Network Management for startup	Slush'd	HIT					Eatable - RobotIT			
Open Innovation	Presence of stable structures for interaction			Punto Impresa		Smact - Unismart	VeniSIA	Liaison Off. Univr		Urban Center	
	Innovation desk analysis & onboarding			Punto Impresa							
	Regular contracts with companies					Smact - Unismart					
	Joint activities implementation			Punto Impresa						Units & OGS	
			Presenza in Gradiente crescente								

Annex 2 - Selection criteria (for Pre-Acc. round 1)

Peso	Pt. min	Pt. MAX	Criterio
15%	3	15	1. Problem identification & relevance
15%	3	15	2. Idea definition and problem-solution fit
5%	1	5	3. Solution novelty
5%	1	5	4. Intellectual Property (IP) Protection
5%	1	5	5. Social and Environmental Impact
15%	3	15	6. Addressable market
0%	0	0	7. Value chain context where the idea takes place
5%	1	5	8. Market Competitiveness and Positioning
0%	0	0	9. Go to market plan (G2MP)
20%	4	20	10. Team Commitment and Execution Capability
5%	1	5	11. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity
10%	2	10	12. Operating model scalability
0%	0	0	13. Investor Appeal and Funding Potential
100 %	20	100	← TOT

Annex 3 - Pre-Acceleration funnel

Effective funnel (number of ideas/startups per Spoke and per process stage):

Spoke	n. ideas / startups (year 1)					Spoke
	in Pre-screening (candidates to the Call et al)	in Screening (compiled the Selection Form)	in evaluation (Committee)	at the Selection Day	1st acceleration programme	
1-BZ	4	4	4	2	2	1-BZ
2-TN	10	7	4	3	2	2-TN
3-UD	20	8	5	2	1	3-UD
4-IUAV	10	7	5	3	2	4-IUAV
5-PD	13	13	5	5	2	5-PD
6-VE	31	10	4	4	1	6-VE
7-VR	19	4	4	4	2	7-VR
8-TS_PAA	62	8	5	5	2	8-TS_PAA
9-SISSA	10	5	4	4	2	9-SISSA
tot	179	66	40	32	16	

Annex 4 - Classification of incoming ideas

Peso	Criteri di classificazione delle idee in entrata
0%	<p>Technology readiness level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL 1 - Basic principles observed • TRL 2 - Technology concept formulated • TRL 3 - Experimental proof of concept • TRL 4 - Technology validated in a lab • TRL 5 - Technology validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) • TRL 6 - Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) • TRL 7 - System prototype demonstration in an operational environment • TRL 8 - System complete and qualified • TRL 9 - Actual system proven in an operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies, or in space)
0%	<p>Business readiness level in general (entry level BRL 2 / 3): to be used by Scouting Specialists (year 2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BRL 1 - Hypotheses of business concepts • BRL 2 - First business concept described, identified overall market and some competitors • BRL 3 - Draft of business model, described market potential & competitive overview • BRL 4 - First version of business model, first projections of economic viability & market potential • BRL 5 - Business model testing, first revenue model, competitive position verified in market • BRL 6 - Full business model including pricing verified on customers • BRL 7 - Product-market fit demonstrated, attractive revenue/cost projections • BRL 8 - Business model is fine-tuned, sales & metrics show business model holds and can scale • BRL 9 - Business model finalised, business scaling with recurring revenues

Annex 5 - Online training materials

Link	Author
https://startupclass.samaltman.com/	Sam Altman (Stanford, 2014)
il Pitch - guida ad una presentazione efficace	Polo tecnologico Alto Adriatico
Il processo di esecuzione di nuove idee	Polo tecnologico Alto Adriatico
Canali di finanziamento per startup	Polo tecnologico Alto Adriatico
Pitch guide video (ITA)	iNEST CC1
Pitch guide video (ITA sub ENG)	iNEST CC1

Annex 6 - Pitch deck template structure

I) CONTEXT

- Problem
- Solution
- Impact
- Market
- Competitors

II) STARTUP

- Governance
- Mission and Vision
- Business Strategy
- Business Model
- Financials

Annex 7 - Quali-quantitative analysis of Spokes internal projects (other than iNEST)

Annex 8 - Patents' analysis

Metodologia analisi brevettuale

Partendo dalla piattaforma Knowledge Share, gli Scouting Specialists effettuano una ricerca sui brevetti più rilevanti, utilizzando alcune parole chiave per i temi dello spoke

Annex 9 - Data elaboration Pre-Acceleration round 1 (descriptive)

